

An Analysis of Qur'anic Sciences during the Sokoto Caliphate Jihad Leaders

*Dr. Muhammad Kabiru Sabo

Department of Shari'ah Studies, Faculty of Arabic and Islamic Studies, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, Nigeria

*Corresponding author: [Dr. Muhammad Kabiru Sabo](#)

Department of Shari'ah Studies, Faculty of Arabic and Islamic Studies, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, Nigeria

Abstract

This study provides a comprehensive analysis of Qur'anic sciences during the Sokoto Caliphate under the leadership of key Jihad figures, focusing specifically on the regions. The objectives of this research is to seeks and explore the educational structures, methods of teaching, and the social impact of Qur'anic sciences during the period of the Sokoto Caliphate Jihad Leaders. The study also investigates how this system of education contributed to the development of Islamic knowledge and society in these regions. This study examines the significance of Qur'anic sciences during the Sokoto Caliphate (1804-1903) under Jihad leaders, notably Usman dan Fodio, Muhammad Bello, and Abdullahi dan Fodio. The results of this research examined the impact of Qur'anic sciences on the Caliphate's development and its status and it concluded. The analytical method was employed in order to have opportunity to analysed the literatures.

Keywords: Qur'an, sciences, Sokoto, Caliphate, Jihad Leaders.

Introduction

Sokoto, Kebbi and Zamfara states are among thirty-six states of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. They are, geographically, located at the north western region of the country. The three states are mostly occupied by Hausa Fulani tribes, and ninety nine percent of the people in the area are Muslims. Thus, Sokoto was the headquarters of the Caliphate established by the 18th century Jihad Leaders under the leadership of *Shaykh* Uthman bn Foduye (May Allah have mercy on him) and his lieutenants, after series of wars between the Jihadists and the rulers of the Hausa kingdom.

The word *Jihad* is an Arabic word from the root “الجهد” which means suffering and exerting. Literally, it means to struggle, to make an effort, to endeavour, to exert. But technically, it means to put up defence against an enemy through any possible way¹. The term *Jihad* leaders therefore refer to the scholars who led people into the struggle for the creation of Sokoto Caliphate under the leadership of *Shaykh* Uthman bn Foduye. *Shaykh* Uthman bn Muhammad Foduye bn Uthman bn Salih bn Harun, a scholar, teacher and reformer was born in the year 1754.C.E in Gobir. He was brought up and taught Qur'an by his father Muhammad Foduye and his mother Hawwa', and later on continued learning from many other scholars of his time. Famous among them was Jibril bn Umar from Agadas in the present Niger Republic. However, Sokoto Caliphate was a system of an Islamic government established by the Sokoto Jihad scholars, after they had defeated and replaced the kingdom of Gobir.²

¹ J. M. Kaura, Sokoto Caliphate Literature in the Context of 19th Century Jihad in Hausa Land, 9th Inaugural lecture, in Auditorium Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, 2009, page 8.

² J. M. Kaura, Sokoto Caliphate Literature in the Context of 19th Century Jihad in Hausa Land, 9th Inaugural lecture, page

There are many gaps between the reviewed literatures and the current research, since the current research is talking about the Qur'anic education during the Sokoto Caliphate but some literatures are discussions on many issues³.

Qur'anic Sciences during the Sokoto Caliphate Jihad Leaders

Shaykh Uthman bn Foduye (May Allah have Mercy on him) came at a time when religious education was very minimal. There were a lot of evil inclinations and mix up of religion with many traditions and cultural beliefs. *Shaykh* Uthman bn Foduye started calling people to the correct teachings of Islam. He challenged the people of his time more especially the scholars on neglecting the education of their children and their wives⁴. In fact, Qur'anic education and science of *Tajwid* were among the areas of knowledge neglected by the people.

Shaykh and his lieutenants strived to change the situation in the area by teaching both males and females the religion of Islam which includes Qur'an and other subjects dealing with other religious obligations, so much that some scholars accused the *Jihad* leaders of allowing co-education which was as they perceived it against the teachings of Islam. Malam 'Abd Allah in reply to such accusation by *Goni* Mustapha from Borno, indicated that they did it out of legal necessity and asked which would be lesser evil, to allow women to remain in total ignorance of their religion or to teach them along with men? They, therefore, penned down books of Islamic Knowledge in order to change the situation. Regarding the Qur'anic sciences⁵. *Shaykh* 'Abd Allah wrote books titled "*Faraid-al-Jalilah*" and "*Miftah-al-Tafsir*" where he explained some concept of *Tajwid* and Qur'anic sciences. For instance, he helped on the need for *Tajwid* in Qur'anic recitation. In his "*Faraid al-Jalilah*, he explained:

Reciting the Glorious Qur'an with *Tajwid* is the Sunnah of the Noble Prophet (Peace and Blessings be upon him). The reason is what was reported regarding Ubay (Companion of the Noble Prophet Peace and Blessings be upon him), when the Messenger of Allah said to him Allah (S.W.T) commanded me to recite the Glorious Qur'an to you. The Companion asked, did Allah mention me with my name. The Messenger of Allah said yes, and recite the Qur'an to him with *Tajwid*. Whoever wants to recite Qur'an, he should make sure that he prepares his voice and recite it with good recitation. You shouldn't chew (the letters of the Qur'an) as cow chews grasses; rather, you should read it with its Arabic form. That is how it was reported from Umar (R.A)⁶.

These are evidences that shows there is existence of Qur'anic education its sciences and application during their period. Also, Qur'anic memorisation was known and there were a number of Qur'anic memorisers during the time. Sultan Muhammad Bello mentioned in his book "*Infaq al-Maisur*" that about two hundred *Qurra'* were killed in the battle of *Tsun-tsuwa*.⁷ He also described his uncle Malam Abd'Allah as "al-Qari'al Mujawwad."⁸

Qur'anic Sciences and Qur'anic schools before colonial Era

Early Qur'anic study is said to be an integral part of the socialisation process of every child. The society expects parents to register their children with a community based Qur'anic School from which at graduation he is expected to recite the Qur'an, read and write Arabic scripts. Where the western system of education exists, the school-age children attend primary schools in the morning and Qur'anic Schools in the afternoon in order to have Qur'anic education⁹.

In most parts of West Africa, the Qur'anic schools predate the coming of the colonialists. Historians put the date of the establishment of such schools to be the early part of the eleventh century C.E. The individual method of teaching was used in the Qur'anic schools. This system allows students to read at his own capacity. The teacher teaches the pupil specific portion of the Qur'an on a wooden slate, the child recites the portion until he has mastered it. He goes back to the teacher and recites the portion to the hearing of his teacher, when the teacher is satisfied of the recital, he then adds more to the ones earlier learned by the pupil. This process continues until he/her finishes the whole Qur'an at his pace¹⁰.

³A. M. Kotorkoshi., "National Musabaqah (Qur'anic Recitation competition): Zamfara state Experience" in Book of proceedings of the first National Conference on the National Qur'anic Recitation Competition in Nigeria, published by Centre for Islamic Studies, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, Nigeria 2017, 33-45.

⁴J. M. Kaura, Sokoto Caliphate Literature in the Context of 19th Century Jihad in Hausa Land, 9th Inaugural lecture, P, 7

⁵J. M. Kaura, Sokoto Caliphate Literature in the Context of 19th Century Jihad in Hausa Land, 9th Inaugural lecture, P, 8.

⁶A. Foduye, Al-Fara'id al-Jalilah wa sa'it al-Fawa'id al-Jamilah Fi 'Ulum al-Qur'an, M.A. Kaigama, et-al (trans) S. Musa (ed.) "selected writings of Shaykh 'Abd Allah bn Foduye, Pp, 72-73.

⁷Bello S.M., Infaq al-Maisur, Muhammad Dan Ige Publication, Sokoto, Nigeria, ND page:119

⁸Bello S.M., Infaq al-Maisur, Muhammad Dan Ige Publication. that is a vast Qur'anic reciter who recites Qur'an with *Tajwid*. page:211.

⁹S. Shehu, Improving Qur'anic (Tsangaya) Education in Nigeria, Trends, Issues, Challenges and The Way Forward, being a Lead Paper Presented at a Three – Day Workshop on Tsangaya System of Education, Organized by the Borno State Agency for Mass Education, Maiduguri, 2nd – 5th May, 2006, Pp, 11-15.

¹⁰Shehu, Improving Qur'anic (Tsangaya) Education in Nigeria, Trends, Issues, Challenges and The Way Forward, P, 12

Next comes the memorisation stage. Initially the student chooses or selects a memorisation stage of a grouping of chapters of the Qur'an that fall within his intelligence and memorisation capacity. He takes his slate for recitation with other experts in attendance; correction is made on orthography and spelling mistakes after which he goes on to individually memorise that portion of the Qur'an he had chosen.

The Qur'anic Sciences and Schools in the Colonial Era

The conquest of West African states by the colonialists not only destroyed the traditional state and political control, but also devastated the entire traditional education set-up. Many scholars, who by their commitment to Islam were part of the Muslim army, were killed in wars of conquest with the colonialists. Many of those that survived, fled into exile.¹¹

The colonialists specifically came up with policies aimed at destroying traditional Qur'anic Schools and replacing them with the western oriented schools. Some people in protest gave their children in trust to the *Ulama'* in Qur'anic schools to go to the village or its outskirts to teach them Qur'an. This is one factor that explains why Qur'anic school teachers travel with young children in search of conducive place to settle and teach these children far away from European schools¹².

The Qur'anic teacher was left as the sole proprietor of the Qur'anic school, to establish, manage, and run them, with the responsibilities of feeding, accommodating and clothing of the children. Initially, students were engaged to work in the teachers' farm, and later farming became an expensive business and the little income received through the weekly contributions of the children's parents could not shoulder the enormous responsibilities rested on the teacher. Students however, were made to pay daily stipends to their teachers; to get this the students were made to carry-out menial jobs in markets and other public places, Hotels etc¹³. The students thus neither got their educational requirement satisfied nor their material needs. They often grow up uneducated (in Islamic education) and unproductive.

Origin and Development of Qur'anic Sciences in Sokoto, Kebbi and Zamfara States

One of the most important developments witnessed in these areas under review during the time of the Sokoto *Jihad* leaders to the Qur'anic education. It is on record that *Shaykh* Abd Allah bn Foduye taught Qur'an and its *Tajwid* to many students. Besides this explanation of the Qur'anic education and its memorisation in books of Tafsir like *Diya' al-Ta'wil Fi Ma'an al-Tanzil* (The light to the interpretation of the Qur'an) and *Kifayah al-Du'fa' al-Sudan Fi Bayan Tafsir al-Qur'an* (What is sufficient for the weak people of the Sudan on explanation of the Qur'an), *Shaykh* Abd Abdallah wrote extensively on 'Ulum al-Qur'an and *Tajwid*. Also, his book *Fara'id al-Jalilah wasa'it al-Fawa'id al-Jamilah* (Selected important issues, and enumerated meritorious things) is enough to serve as an example on how great they propagated the Qur'anic education in the areas of study and the region in general.¹⁴

Makarantun Allo (traditional Islamiyya School) were locally opened as was the usual practice at that time by the disciples of *Jihad* leaders where the recitation and memorisation of Qur'an with *Tajwid* was taught in line with other branches of knowledge.

Qur'anic education has been deeply entrenched for many centuries in the territories of Kanem Borno and Sokoto Caliphates, which form the present day Northern Nigeria which include Sokoto, Kebbi and Zamfara states. This system of education impacted greatly on the thoughts, values and way of life of the peoples of these three states. Colonialism brought new issues and challenges in the process of acquiring and disseminating Qur'anic education¹⁵.

Islamic and Qur'anic education is synonymous because Islam is the Din while Qur'an is the book of Islam. In fact, whoever is acquiring Islamic education must primarily acquire it with the Qur'anic education as a convert or a young Muslim. So, the history of Islamic education is going along with Qur'anic education. Islam came to Nigeria through the North African traders.¹⁶ Therefore, as Fafunwa asserted, from the advent of Islam in Nigeria in the 11th century, Islamic (Qur'anic) educational development reached its peak in the 15th to 16th century. The keen interest of Mai Dunama of Ngazargamu in Islamic education; the Mai Idris Aloma's carry forward; the Yakubu's and Muhammad Rumfa's effort in Kano and the activities of Muhammad. Danmasani and Muhammad Danmarina under the influence of Al- Maghili in

¹¹ Shehu, Improving Qur'anic (Tsangaya) Education In Nigeria, Trends, Issues, Challenges And The Way Forward, P, 13

¹² Shehu, Improving Qur'anic (Tsangaya) Education In Nigeria, Trends, Issues, Challenges And The Way Forward, P, 14.

¹³ Shehu, Improving Qur'anic (Tsangaya) Education In Nigeria, Trends, Issues, Challenges And The Way Forward, P, 15,

¹⁴ A. Y, Muhammad, Ilm alTajwid and Qur'anic Recitation competition in Northern Nigeria, UDUS, 2009, p, 50.

¹⁵ Shehu, Improving Qur'anic (Tsangaya) Education In Nigeria, Trends, Issues, Challenges And The Way Forward, P, 51

¹⁶ A. Fafunwa, The History of Education in Nigeria, 1991, London: George Allen. P, 53

Katsina were living evidence of this assertion...¹⁷. In Nigeria, a hundred percent of the Islamic education is. Firstly, in the Qur'anic studies. As Fafunwa described¹⁸..."the Muslim child at his earlier life begins to learn the shorter chapters of the Qur'an for the performance of five daily prayers. He learns the chapters by heart through repetition and by rote as the first stage of the education. The next, stage is learning the Arabic alphabets, which involve knowing, pronouncing and the formation of syllables with vowels. After this stage, one may be able to read the Qur'an off-hand. As one can read through the pages without difficulties, that is not the end. One needs to know the meaning of the chapters, their exegesis and the sciences of recitation (Tajwid) and so it goes.

The above description of the Qur'anic education system of learning can be regarded as conventional. Visiting other Muslim schools in other countries will reveal the same thing. So, it is happening in Sudan, Malaysia and so on. Even in European countries like America, Britain and the rest, Qur'anic education follows the same evolution. In Britain for example, Sarwar stated that¹⁹ as new Muslim communities began to form, the need to educate children according to their religious tradition, Qur'anic Madrasahs were established in many British mosques. As a result, Madrasahs have been an established institutions in British mosques for almost half a century. Madrasahs in the British Muslim context usually act as part-time schools offering evening and weekend classes, are normally located within the mosque, and are attended by children to learn the recitation of the Qur'an. Woodward (1996:149-154), also asserted... Children often attend madrasahs for several years, often completing the recitation of whole Qur'an a number of times. Attendance of madrasahs on a regular basis has a nurturing effect on the children, familiarizing them with their religious identity, connecting them to their religious centre, the mosque²⁰.

The contributions of contemporary Sokoto, Kebbi and Zamfara states scholars in the field of Qur'anic education is very great considering the situation of this particular field of study in the previous years. From 70s to 2020, Muslims in Sokoto, Kebbi and Zamfara witnessed tremendous development of Qur'anic education. This well perhaps lead us to the discussion of the origin and development of Qur'anic education in Sokoto, Kebbi and Zamfara states.

Origin and Development of Qur'anic Sciences in Sokoto, Kebbi and Zamfara States in the post Jihad leaders from 1980 to 2020

After the role played by the *Jihad* leaders of Sokoto caliphate, (The Triumvirate) towards the development of Qur'anic education and memorisation, Muslims became so acquainted with the Qur'anic education and memorisation. This phenomenon continued until 1903, C.E when British Colonialism destroyed the Caliphate, and a number of Islamic values were distorted. Islamic education all system was replaced by the Western education which takes away the attention of Muslim youth from engaging themselves in acquiring Islamic education. This no doubt causes negative effects to Islamic education in general and Qur'anic education and memorisation in particular. The legacy left by the *Jihad* leaders towards Qur'anic education and memorisation started declining to the minimal stage so much that *Tajwid* was not fully implemented when reciting the Glorious Qur'an and some were in total disagreement with the science of *Al-Tajwid* as part of Qur'anic education²¹.

The 1960 independence became another stage of Qur'anic education revival and promotion of Qur'anic teaching and memorisation in Northern Nigeria, Sokoto, Kebbi and Zamfara states inclusive.

Furthermore, despite the declining nature of Qur'anic education, the following are said to be factors responsible for the revival as well as development of Qur'anic education and Tajwid in Sokoto, Kebbi and Zamfara:

1. Efforts of some foreign Muslim Scholars

In the 19th century, the field of Qur'anic education flourished and developed through the efforts of some foreign scholars from Saudi Arabia, Egypt, Pakistan and Sudan among others, who were invited by the successive Governments of Northern Nigeria to come and teach both in the O' level and tertiary institutions. Arabic institutions particularly were established in places like Kano, Katsina, Sokoto and Kebbi. Schools like Sultan Abubakar College Sokoto (S.A.C), College of Arts and Arabic Studies (C.A.A.S) now *Shaykh* Abubakar Gummi Memorial College), and later on in the 20th century the institution like centre for Islamic Studies Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto and College of Education Sokoto (now Shehu Shagari College of Education, all witnessed the presence of some foreign Qur'an scholars who greatly contributed to the development of Qur'anic education in Sokoto, Kebbi and Zamfara states. For instance, *Shaykh* Muhammad Hassan Sulaiman, a teacher at College of Arts and Arabic Studies Sokoto (C.A.A.S) in the early 70s, organised lessons of Qur'anic recitation, memorisation and *Tajwid* for beginners at different places in Sokoto such as

¹⁷ H. A Alkali, Note on Arabic Teaching in Northern Nigeria, Kano Studies No. 3. 1967, P, 22

¹⁸ A. Fafunwa, The History of Education in Nigeria, Op. Cit, Pp, 60-61

¹⁹ G. Sarwar, British Muslims and Schools. London: The Muslim Education al Trust, 1994, P, 28.

²⁰ G. Sarwar, British Muslims and Schools. London: The Muslim Education al Trust P, 29.

²¹ G. Sarwar, British Muslims and Schools. London: The Muslim Education al Trust P, 29

Sultan Abubakar College, College of Arts and Arabic Studies and Giginya Memorial College which were attended by many interested students from Sokoto, Kebbi and Zamfara states²².

Just like *Shaykh* Sulaiman did, al *Shaykh* Abd Allah al-Zawawi, a lecturer with the College of Education (now Shehu Shagari College of Education) organised similar Qur'an and *Tajwid* lessons at various places in Sokoto, such as College of education Sokoto, *Masallacin Alhazzai* and at his residence. All these took place almost during the same period in the late 70s and 80s.

2. Creation of Embassies of Arab countries in the Nigeria: After Nigeria became an independent nation many Arab nations opened their Embassies and Consulates for diplomatic relations. As a result, Nigerians particularly the Northerners became in contact with the Arabs who some of them were Qur'anic memorisers and *Tajwid* teachers²³.

3. Studying in Arab countries: With the relationship between Nigeria and Arab countries, students from Nigeria used to go to such countries like Egypt, Sudan, Saudi Arabia purposely for acquiring Islamic and Arabic knowledge. Some of these students had already memorised the Glorious Qur'an and learnt *Tajwid* before returning home like Abubakar Abubakar Isah, Abdulaziz Shehu Kofar Rini known as Abdulaziz Ahlu *Shaykh*, Malami Abdullahi Gidadawa, Attahiru Muhammad Marnona among others²⁴.

4. Musabaqah (Qur'an Recitation Competition) paid much impact and development in Qur'anic education and memorisation in the areas of study in the sense that some efforts were made by some visiting and indigenous scholars in the Qur'anic teaching and memorisation using different ways and methodologies. For example, in 1984 a group of concern scholars of Sokoto State origin established a committee which task was to organize a *Musabaqah* in celebrating certain occasions such as marriage and naming ceremonies within the locality of Sokoto metropolis with the aim of advocating the science of *Tajwid* and Qur'an memorisation among the people. Even though the then competition was centred on the application of science of *Tajwid* in Qur'an recitation, Memorisation was not the primary objective of the competition. The committee was chaired by late Malam Abu-Bakr Usman *Nupawa*, Malam Abubakar Ali Bakura as secretary and Malam Sidi A. Sidi as P.R.O.²⁵

The national Qur'an recitation competition established in the year 1986 (by the Centre for Islamic studies, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto) the first of its kind in the nation contributed towards the spread of *Tahfidh* and *Tajwid* in the state. The competition was organized with the aim of boosting the moral of the Muslim youths towards memorizing the Glorious Qur'an in accordance with *Tajwid*.²⁶ As a result, many Muslim youths were engaged in learning the procedure and principles of Qur'an recitation as well as its memorisation, not only in Sokoto state but in Nigeria as a whole. However, during the period Kebbi and Zamfara states were not carved out of Sokoto at that time. So, whatever to obtained in Sokoto is likely the reflection in those states that formed part of the current study. The competition was in the first place held in Sokoto in the year 1986,²⁷ Borno in 1987, Kano in 1988, Oyo in 1989, Bauchi in 1990, Plateau in 1991, Lagos in 1992, Katsina in 1993, Niger In 1994, Kaduna in 1995, Abuja in 1996, Ogun in 1997, 1998/1999 Adamawa, kwara in 2000, Sokoto in 2001, Zamfara in 2002, Nasarawa in 2003, Yobe in 2003/2004 Kebbi in 2004, Kano in 2005, Bauchi in 2005, Sokoto in 2007, Kaduna 2007, Edo in 2008/2009, Sokoto in 2010, Jigawa in 2011, Katsina in 2012, Zamfara in 2013, Jigawa in 2014, Edo in 2015, Nasarawa in 2016, Kwara in 2017, Katsina in 2018, Gombe in 2019, Legos in 2020, Kano in 2021, Bauchi in 2022, Zamfara in 2022/2023.²⁸

As a result of the competition, the Sokoto state government Under ministry of education appointed a coordinator of Qur'an recitation competition at the state level, also each local government appointed coordinator for the competition whose responsibility is to search for Qur'an memorisers from various schools. This development encouraged many

²² A. Garba, The contributions of some Muslim Scholars to the Development of ITajwid and Memorisation of the Qur'an in Kebbi state between 1980 to 2008, M. A Dissertation submitted to the Department of Islamic Studies, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, 2010, P, 68

²³ . Garba, The contributions of some Muslim Scholars to the Development of ITajwid and Memorisation of the Qur'an in Kebbi state between 1980 to 2008, P, 68

²⁴ . Garba, The contributions of some Muslim Scholars to the Development of ITajwid and Memorisation of the Qur'an in Kebbi state between 1980 to 2008, P, 69

²⁵ Malam Abubakar Ali Bakura, (77years), Islamic preacher and farmer, Interviewed at his house, Dallatu Road, Tudun wada area, Sokoto, 24/January, 2023 at 2:30pm

²⁶ Status of the Centre for Islamic Studies, reviewed in 1997. Page: 2

²⁷ Status of the Centre for Islamic Studies, P, 3.

²⁸ B. Abubakar, Historical Origin of Tajwid and Tahfidh in Sokoto State and the Role of Musabaqah (Qur'an Recitation Competition) Towards its Development, in Sarcouncil Journal of Education and Sociology, Vol. 01-2023, Published: 16-01-2023, P, 4.

schools to pay much attention in teaching their students and guiding them to the appropriate way of reciting the Glorious Qur'an as well as its memorisation²⁹.

Furthermore, Arabic and Islamic education Board contributed immensely to the development of Qur'an memorisation through organizing competitions right from local government up to the state levels. Forty-six (six) participants both males and females are expected to participate in each category from the twenty-three (23) local government of the state, cash and kind gifts are being presented at the closing ceremony which encourage the youth to pay much attention to the memorisation of the Glorious Qur'an. This resulted to a number of memorisers among the youth in different areas of the state³⁰.

In Kebbi state, *Musabaqah* had no doubt increased the efforts of the memorisers and all other stakeholders in the search for Qur'anic and its *Tajwid*. Moreover, the number of Qur'anic memorisers has been increasing annually since the inception of *Musabaqah* to date. This can be observed considering the number of the participants at all levels from different places across the country including Kebbi state. Numerous Islamiyyah schools were opened and operate *Tahfidh* and *Tajwid* program in so places.

In Zamfara state *Musabaqah* played a vital role in improving in Qur'anic education and its memorisation. Even though, before the inception of *Musabaqah* in Nigeria and in particular, Qur'anic education is taught by *Malams* in Hausaland,³¹ Zamfara inclusive, but without proper care to the principles of *Tajwid*. However, due to the impact of *Musabaqah*, many have learnt the art of Qur'anic recitation, especially the youth. In those days, very few were able to read Qur'an with appropriate *Tajwid* rules and regulations in Gusau and various local Governments of Zamfara state, but today, they are hundreds. This is because of most of the former participants of *Musabaqah* are now teachers in their respective schools. Plethora of people do memorise Qur'an even before the beginning of *Musabaqah*, yet, it encourages it to higher level. For instance, Sadiq Siddiq posited that before he went for International *Musabaqah* at Saudi Arabia, his school has a great number of students with over thirty classes, but only two classes were meant for memorisation. But, after his success in *Musabaqah*, more students were brought and three additional classes for memorisation were added. In fact, he maintained that, today the number of classes meant for different branches of knowledge were equal to that of memorisation classes.

Interestingly, female students were not included in memorisation, but today, almost 30 to 40 female students memorised the entire Qur'an annually at his *Zawiyyah* Gusau.³² With this development and impact of *Musabaqah*, many schools were opened for the purpose of memorisation in these three states. Before, the inception of *Musabaqah*, schools for Qur'anic memorisation in Sokoto, Kebbi and Zamfara states were not many, but today, the areas of study were blessed with schools for the purpose of memorisation which led to the gigantic level of Qur'anic education and memorisation.

The Result

The analysis of Qur'anic education during the Sokoto Caliphate, particularly under the leadership of the Jihad leaders such as Usman dan Fodio, his son Muhammad Bello, and his brother Abdullahi dan Fodio, reveals a robust and transformative educational system deeply rooted in Islamic principles. Qur'anic education was central to the social, political, and religious life of the Caliphate, serving not only as a tool for spiritual guidance but also as a means of societal reform and intellectual development.

The results of Qur'anic sciences during the Sokoto Caliphate include: Emphasis on Islamic Knowledge and Scholarship

The Jihad leaders prioritized the study and teaching of the Qur'an as the foundation of education. They established numerous schools, mosques, and learning centers dedicated to Qur'anic education, emphasizing memorization, recitation, and understanding of the Qur'an. This educational emphasis extended to Hadith (traditions of the Prophet Muhammad), Fiqh (Islamic jurisprudence), and other Islamic sciences, fostering a scholarly environment that valued deep religious knowledge.

²⁹ A comprehensive result of the State *Musabaqah* of, 1998 to 2009 compiled by the office of the co- Coordinator Qur'anic Recitation Competition Arabic and Islamic Education Board Sokoto.

³⁰ A comprehensive result of the State *Musabaqah* of, 1998 to 2009 compiled by the office of the co- Coordinator Qur'anic Recitation Competition.

³¹ L. Jimoh, "Towards Standardisation of the Indigenous Qur'anic Intonations Employed by Reciters in Nigeria", in Jimoh (ed) Contemporary Muslims' Beliefs and Practices: Between Orthodoxy and Syncretism, Department of Religion and Peace Studies, L.A.S.U. Lagos. 2013, p, 188.

³² Goni, Sadiq Siddiq, (47years), Business man, Jumu'at Mosque of Sanami Gusau and Judge at Local, State, National and International *Musabaqah*. Interviewed via phone call on 20/01/2023, at 5:33pm.

Promotion of Literacy and Widespread Access to Education

The Sokoto Caliphate leaders encouraged broad access to education for both men and women. Qur'anic schools (Madrasas) were established across the Caliphate, and education was not limited to the elite. Women were actively involved in education, and there are numerous records of prominent female scholars, teachers, and poets during the period. This emphasis on education for all promoted literacy and created a well-informed society.

Integration of Qur'anic Sciences with Social and Political Reform**

Qur'anic education during the Sokoto Caliphate was not only religious but also tied to social justice and political reform. The Jihad leaders used the Qur'an as a guiding document to advocate for ethical governance, social justice, and community welfare. They emphasized moral conduct, honesty, and the responsibilities of leadership, viewing education as a tool to mold ethical and pious leaders who would govern in accordance with Islamic values.

Development of a Written Tradition and Islamic Scholarship**

The era of the Sokoto Jihad saw a significant increase in Islamic scholarship and written works. The Jihad leaders themselves were prolific writers, producing numerous works on theology, jurisprudence, education, ethics, and governance. These writings, often rooted in Qur'anic teachings, became essential texts for the educational curriculum in the Caliphate. Arabic was the primary language of scholarship, but the use of the local language, Hausa, in education also flourished, making Islamic knowledge more accessible to the wider population.

Institutionalization of Sciences and the Establishment of Learning Centres

The Caliphate established a formal structure for Islamic education, with schools and educational centers set up in urban and rural areas. Teachers were respected and often funded by the state or supported through community contributions, reflecting the high value placed on education. These institutions became centers for intellectual exchange, producing scholars who traveled throughout West Africa, spreading Islamic knowledge and the educational methods of the Sokoto Caliphate.

Resistance to Colonial Influences through Islamic Education

Even after the peak of the Caliphate's power, Qur'anic education played a crucial role in resisting colonial influence. The emphasis on Islamic education helped preserve cultural and religious identity during a period of external pressures and change, creating a legacy that persisted well beyond the Caliphate's political dominance.

In summary, Qur'anic education during the Sokoto Caliphate under the leadership of the Jihad leaders was a dynamic and influential system that integrated religious instruction with societal transformation. It promoted literacy, scholarship, and social reform while strengthening Islamic identity and governance. The legacy of this educational system had a profound and lasting impact on West African Islamic culture, leaving a tradition of learning that continues to be celebrated in the region today.

Conclusion

In conclusion, Qur'anic education during the Sokoto Caliphate under the leadership of the Jihad leaders was a transformative force that not only advanced Islamic knowledge but also fostered social reform, literacy, and a strong sense of religious and cultural identity. It was deeply integrated into the governance and daily life of the Caliphate, promoting both spiritual and ethical development. The emphasis on accessible education for all, including women, and the production of a rich body of Islamic scholarship, solidified the region's intellectual legacy. This educational focus not only empowered the community through a shared Islamic framework but also laid the foundation for enduring religious and cultural resilience, influencing the West African Islamic landscape long after the height of the Caliphate's political power.

Bibliography

1. Abubakar, B. (2023), Historical Origin of Tajwid and Tahfidh in Sokoto State and the Role of Musabaqah (Qur'an Recitation Competition) Towards its Development, in Sarcouncil Journal of Education and Sociology, Vol. 01.
2. Alkali, H. A (1967), Note on Arabic Teaching in Northern Nigeria, Kano Studies No. 3.
3. Bello S.M., (ND), Infaq al-Maisur, Muhammad Dan Ige Publication, Sokoto, Nigeria,
4. Foduye, A. (2010), Al-Fara'id al-Jalilah wa sa'it al-Fawa'id al-Jamilah Fi 'Ulum al-Qur'an, M.A. Kaigama, et-al (trans) S. Musa (ed.) "selected writings of Shaykh 'Abd Allah bn Foduye,
5. Fafunwa, A. (1991), The History of Education in Nigeria, London: George Allen.
6. Garba, A. (2010), The contributions of some Muslim Scholars to the Development of ITajwid and Memorisation of the Qur'an in Kebbi state between 1980 to 2008, M. A Dissertation Department of Islamic Studies, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto.
7. Jimoh, L. (2013), "Towards Standardisation of the Indigenous Qur'anic Intonations Employed by Reciters in Nigeria", in Jimoh (ed) Contemporary Muslims' Beliefs and Practices: Between Orthodoxy and Syncretism, Department of Religion and Peace Studies, L.A.S.U. Lagos.

8. Kaura, J. M. (2009), Sokoto Caliphate Literature in the Context of 19th Century Jihad in Hausa Land, 9th Inaugural lecture, in Auditorium Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto
9. Kotorkoshi. A. M. (2017,) "National Musabaqah (Qur'anic Recitation competition): Zamfara state Experience" in Book of proceedings of the first National Conference on the National Qur'anic Recitation Competition in Nigeria, published by Centre for Islamic Studies, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, Nigeria.
10. Muhammad, A. Y, (2009), *Ilm al-Tajwid and Qur'anic Recitation competition in Northern Nigeria*, UDUS
11. Sarwar, G. (1994), *British Muslims and Schools*. London: The Muslim Education al Trust.
12. Shehu, S. (2006), *Improving Qur'anic (Tsangaya) Education in Nigeria, Trends, Issues, Challenges and the Way Forward*, being a Lead Paper Presented at a Three – Day Workshop on Tsangaya System of Education, Organized by the Borno State Agency for Mass Education, Maiduguri.